

in the plot. Certain panicles in affected hills also suffered from sheath rot or bacterial leaf blight, but no correlation with panicle sterility could be traced. Diseased panicles sometimes set normal grains. Soil samples from affected and normal hills did not show any difference in nematode populations.

Symptoms were observed during 1980-81 and 1981-82 kharif, in different plots of the Jokhihat block, Purnea district, North Bihar. ■

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute concise summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two pages and no more than two short tables, figures, or photographs. Contributions are subject to editing and abridgement to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Disease resistance

Resistance to blast and brown spot in Karnataka

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Wide distribution of blast and brown spot diseases in an epiphytotic form causes severe damage at all stages of the rice crop in many areas of Karnataka. Considerable variation in resistance to leaf blast, neck blast, and brown spot diseases occurred in 69 varieties screened during 1981 kharif. Twenty-four varieties were found resistant to leaf and neck blast disease (see table). Twenty-five varieties were found resistant to brown spot disease. Of the 69 varieties screened, only 9 showed resistance to all 3 diseases. ■

Resistance of released and unreleased varieties of rice to blast and brown spot in Karnataka

Variety	Disease score ^a		
	Leaf blast	Neck blast	Brown spot
IET3116	M	R	R
IET3305	R	M	M
IET3195	R	M	M
IET2685	R	M	M
IET2490	R	R	R
IET4699	R	R	M
IET4155	R	R	M
IET3280	M	M	R
IET3626	R	R	R
ET4094	R	R	R
IET1789	R	R	R
IET4107	R	M	R

Variety	Disease score ^a		
	Leaf blast	Neck blast	Brown spot
IET2684	R	M	R
IET5725	R	R	R
IET2444	R	R	R
IET6211	M	R	R
IET5656	M	M	M
IET5890	R	R	M
IET5854	R	R	M
IET3629	R	M	M
IET2700	R	R	R
IET2730	M	R	M
IET4555	R	R	M
IET2570	M	M	M
IET5722	R	R	M
IET4592	R	R	M
IET5704	R	M	M
IET5721	M	M	M
IET2246	R	M	M
IET5853	M	M	M
KMP32	R	R	M
KMP41	M	R	M
KMP47	R	R	M
KMP63	M	R	M
KMP64	R	R	M
KMP65	R	M	M
KMP67	R	R	M
KMP68	R	R	M
KMP70	M	R	M
KMP73	R	R	M
KMP74	R	M	M
KMP75	R	R	M
KMP42	M	R	R
83-KMP (A) 57	R	M	M
CR222-MR-10	M	M	M
CR165-18-8	M	M	M
ES-6	M	M	M
ES-18	R	M	R
ES-24	M	M	M
IR6115-1-1-1	M	M	M
Improved Madhu	M	M	M
IR8	M	M	R
S705	M	S	R
Mahsuri	M	S	M
Intan	R	R	R
Cauvery	M	S	M
Jagnath	R	S	R

Variety	Disease score ^a		
	Leaf blast	Neck blast	Brown spot
S-22	R	R	R
Madhu	R	M	M
TN1	R	M	R
Pragathi	R	M	M
MR401	M	M	R
MR362	M	R	R
MR261	R	M	R
MR343	M	M	M
Sona	R	M	R
Vani	M	R	R
ADT32	R	M	M
IR3941-8-1	R	R	M

^aR = resistant, M = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible.

Properties and concentrations of rice bunchy stunt virus

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The properties of rice bunchy stunt virus (RBSV) were determined by bioassay that involves injecting a virus source into the abdomen of *Nephotettix cincticeps*, using a capillary glass needle provided by IRRI. Virus sources were prepared by homogenizing diseased materials in 0.1 M phosphate buffer solution (pH 7.0).

Infectivity of insects indicated that the dilution end point of RBSV was 10⁻⁴ of the diseased leaves and 10⁻³ of viruliferous insects. The thermal inactivation point was 60° C and longevity in vitro was 4 days at 0-4° C.

Ratios of infective to noninfective insects were 5:20 when they were injected with diseased leaves, 2:19 with diseased leaf sheaths, 1:21 with diseased roots, and 0:22 with diseased stems. The concentration of the virus seemed to be

higher in the leaves. Injection of sap from diseased plant leaves inoculated 10 days earlier gave a ratio of 1 to 13; 20 days earlier, 2:21; 30 days earlier, 4:20; 40 days earlier, 3:19; 50 days earlier, 1:17; and 60 days earlier, 1:22.

When injected with the sap of viruliferous insects 5 days after acquisition feeding, infective insects were 0:17; 10 days after, 0:18; 15 days after, 3:20; 20 days after, 4:12; 25 days after, 7:15; and 30 days after, 2:5. ■

Tungro incidence in Bihar and West Bengal, India

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A severe incidence of tungro virus disease occurred during 1981 kharif in parts of Bihar and West Bengal (see figure). Disease incidence was 40-100% in Bihar and 60-100% in West Bengal.

Transmission tests of samples collected from different locations were conducted to identify the virus. About 50 nonviruliferous *Nephotettix virescens* were confined on each sample for 48 hours, then on 10-day-old Taichung (Native) 1 seedlings for 24 hours. Typi-

cal symptoms of tungro virus developed within 7-10 days.

In North Bihar, the popular local variety Bakol was observed to be highly susceptible to tungro. Among the high-yielding semidwarf varieties grown in the area, Jaya, Pankaj, and Sita were susceptible; Rajendra Dhan 201 and Saket 4 were tolerant. Local improved variety BR34 was fairly tolerant. Disease incidence was higher in wetlands than in drylands.

In West Bengal, IR8, Jaya, and Mahsuri were highly susceptible to tungro. Local varieties Dorangi, Pankalash, Raghusail, and Patnai 23 were susceptible. A few local varieties — Mugh, Bismoni, Kartiksail, and Tillakachari — appeared resistant. ■

Rice gall dwarf virus occurrence in Peninsular Malaysia

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During a survey of rice virus disease incidence in January 1982, a number of rice plants showing characteristic symptoms of rice gall dwarf disease were observed at MARDI Rice Research Station, Bumbong Lima. The undersurface of leaf blades showed typical light green, almost round galls or vein-swelling (see figure). Infected plants were stunted, had fewer tillers, and appeared darker green than surrounding healthy plants.

A latex agglutination test used latex sensitized with antisera against rice gall dwarf virus prepared from a virus isolate from Thailand. A positive reaction showed that both viruses were serologically similar, confirming the presence of rice gall dwarf virus in Peninsular Malaysia. ■

Tungro outbreak in Bihar and West Bengal, India, in 1981.

Light green galls on undersurface of leaves of gall dwarf virus-infected rice plant.